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NEW METHODS FOR EVALUATING EMOTIONAL EXPERIENCE IN THE PRODUCT DESIGN PROCESS

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, users' needs have been recognized as valuable parameters for product design. Hence, capturing user experiences and emotions are essential to design pleasant products. The present study focused on user experience and how it can be captured during the use of product. It aimed to introduce two new types of emotional evaluation methods that can be used to examine and understand user experiences while they are interacting with the products. The two novel methods are called; *Kansei* sheets, and Read Body Language sheet. The results of this study will be of interest for design educators, and decision makers.

Keywords: Evaluation Methods, Emotions, User Experience, Product Design.

INTRODUCTION

Emotions pervade our daily life. They can help us guide our choices, avoid a danger and they also play a key role in non-verbal communication. Assessing emotions is thus essential to the understanding of human behavior and need. Emotion assessment is a rapidly growing research field, especially in the area of human product interaction (HPI) (Guillaume, et al., 2006). Nowadays, there are few techniques for gathering affective data (Eva & Muriel, 2007). In this paper, we introduced and discussed new methods to interpret and assess emotional and physical responses of users while they are interacting with the products. Our measurement methods provide interactive designers and researchers with valuable information about a user easily. To demonstrate how to use our new emotional evaluation methods, a workshop was carried out at Kyushu University.

METHODS

KANSEI SHEETS

They are visual measurement tools (Figure 1). Sheet #1 aims to measure the emotional responses of a user while he or she is interacting with a product. Sheet #2 aims to measure physical responses of users. On sheet #1, the user's emotional responses are measured according to a Likert-type scale: I feel this to some extent (10%); I feel this (40%); I feel this very much (70%); and I strongly feel this (100%). On sheet #2, the user's physical responses are measured according to a similar Likert-type scale: I suffer somewhat from this (10%); I suffer from this (40%); I suffer from this very much (70%); and I strongly suffer from this (100%). Through using these sheets, participants will be able to recognize all emotional and physical responses in two differentiated components; qualitative and quantitative. The two sheets can be used cross-culturally because they do not ask respondents to verbalize their emotions.

READ BODY LANGUAGE (RBL) SHEET

This tool was proposed to be used by a designer to understand the users and their non-verbal communications/behaviors (Figure 2). In other words, it aims to interpret users' dynamic expressions by observing them while they are interacting with a product. Based on the ten emotion heuristics (TEH) (Eva & Muriel, 2007) and several studies regarding human emotions (Tingfan, 2009) and (Cynthia & Martinovich, 2002), 20 distinct emotional responses were interpreted and analyzed in one sheet which is called "read body language RBL sheet".

WORKSHOP DETALIS

1 (10%), 2 (30%), 3 (70%), and 4 (100%) “Emotion Degree”
 T1, T2, T3, and T4 “Tasks”— The users were asked to do different tasks for evaluating a product

Figure 1. The Product Emotion Measurement Method (Kansei Sheets)

	U1	U2	U3	U4
T1				
T1				
T1				
T2				
T2				
T2				
T3				
T3				
T3				
T4				
T4				
T4				

T1, T2, T3, and T4 “Tasks to do” U1, U2, U3, and U4 “Users Number”

Figure 2. The Product Emotion Measurement Method (Read Body Language Sheet)

The workshop (WS) aimed to introduce new methods for designing pleasant product and user experience. It was carried out in a laboratory in Kyushu University in June 2010. A blood pressure (BP) device was selected as a case study. The workshop was done in three stages (Figure 3); capture, develop, and present. Four users (20 to 30 years old) were asked to evaluate the device’s usability, and its appearance (including size, color and shape).

In the first stage “Capture”, each user was asked five questions: First one was regarding aesthetics appeal of a BP device – “Q.1 Is this design of a BP device attractive for you?” Second, third and fourth questions were about product usability– “Q.2 Can you set up this device?”, “Q.3 Can you measure your blood pressure?”, and “Q. 4 Can you dismantle the device and pack it back into the original state? The fifth question was about the device value – “Q.5 What do you think about the value of this device?” Three different elements were measured for understanding and identifying user’s Kansei: a) internal emotional and conscious physical responses, b) body language, and c) spoken words. The following different methods were used to measure each element respectively; Kansei sheets, RBL sheet, and user interview.

First and second methods were firstly used together “at the same time”. Then, interviews were conducted to identify the reasons behind the positive and negative emotional responses of each user. The collected data of the above different methods were compared and analyzed.

In the second stage of the workshop “Develop”, based on the findings of the former step, unique and

pleasant ideas were suggested for the new design of the BP device. As for the third stage of the workshop “Present”, the best ideas were presented and discussed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Using emotions is tricky. As Pieter Desmet points out, “there is no one-to-one relationship between the design of a product and the emotion it elicits. An emotion is not elicited by a product as such, but by the appraised significance of this product for our concerns”. The basic fact is well-known, for many products induce strong, but contradictory emotions in different people - some loving it, some intensely disliking it. This means that different products will satisfy different classes of people, or different setting and usages. A colorfully decorated lunch pail would work just as well for children as for distinguished business executives, but the executives might very well judge the pail to be emotionally pleasing and fun for the children while simultaneously viewing it with contempt for themselves. Here, the same product receives different emotional assessment even by the same person when the intended role of the product is changed (Pieter, 2006 & Donald, 2003).

Recently, in Japan, the results of several studies regarding healthcare sector found that some medical devices are difficult to use and have unattractive design. This may lie in the fact that some companies haven’t gained sufficient insight into users’ needs (Japan External trade Organization, 2006).

Therefore, the WS stages focused on redesigning a BP device that is currently used in Japan. In the WS, three stages were carried out as follows:

Figure 3. Workshop Stages

Stage 1 of WS: Capture the users' experiences and problems

In this stage, five questions were asked to each user throughout three evaluation levels; visceral, behavioral, and reflective (Norman, 2003). These levels were created by Donald A. Norman.

First: Visceral Level (superficial first impression):

We asked users one question in order to evaluate the device appearance and aesthetics "aesthetics experience"; "Q.1 is this design of a BP device attractive for you?" In other words, how the product (whether new design or current design) looks, feels and sounds. Each user was asked to use *Kansei* sheet #1 to perform this task.

Second: Behavioral Level (usage of product):

We asked users three questions in order to evaluate product usability and functionality "experience of usability". The questions are; Can you set up this device?", "Q.3 Can you measure your blood pressure?", and "Q. 4 Can you dismantle the device and pack it back into the original state? In this level, each user was asked to use *Kansei* sheets # 1 and 2 to carry out the tasks.

Third: Reflective Level (overall impression / the meaning of things):

Emotional product experience is as dynamic as the human-product interaction itself. Products do not elicit a single emotion but complex emotional episodes. The emotional impact of a product 'as such' differs from the emotional episode elicited by product usage. For designers it is relevant to understand the holistic nature of this emotional episode. We cannot simply break down the interaction into a sequence of actions because emotion in a particular action is determined by all previous actions. You can compare it to reading a book. The emotions experienced at any point of time are not just elicited by the particular page one is reading, but by all previous pages that have already been read (Pieter, 2006).

Therefore, in this level, we asked users to evaluate a product as a whole, including its value and importance for him or her "experience of meaning". In addition, what does using this product say about you (or user)? This level of evaluation is essential for creating things we want to show off to our friends.

Sheet # 1 was used by each user to achieve this evaluation level.

In first stage of WS, the designers observed the users during their interaction with the device. Designers used the RBL sheet in order to understand the meaning of users' emotional responses. The main results of this stage revealed the following (Figures 4 and 5);

- In terms of observable body language (including outward facial expressions), there are two different types of users' emotional responses; visible and no visible. In case of visible responses, the RBL sheet enabled us to interpret outward facial and body expressions of many participants. However, we found some difficulty in interpreting emotional responses of some participants.
- The comparison that was done between the collected data of *Kansei* sheets and the RBL sheet revealed that the inner emotional responses (heart / mind) and the outer emotional responses (outward facial expressions) of some participants were different. In other words, visible reactions of some participants were not correctly interpreted and were thus misunderstood. The reason is that obvious facial and body expressions of those participants did not precisely reflect their true internal emotional responses.

It can be said that the collected data of *Kansei* sheets helped us to understand the true emotional responses of all participants, especially people who misread their emotional responses and others whose emotions were not visible to us. We could recognize all emotional and physical responses in two differentiated components; qualitative and quantitative. The first component is regarding the identification of the emotional (happiness, anger, etc.) and physical (sweat, headache, etc.) signatures. On the other hand, the second component is regarding the degree of each emotional (such as; I feel this to some extent, I feel this, I feel this very much, and I strongly feel this) and physical signature (such as; I suffer from this to some extent, I suffer from this, I suffer from this very much, and I strongly suffer from this).

According to the above finding, designers need to use several methods together for capturing

comprehensive information of user experience. Using only one method or relying on designers' observation may lead to defective results of user experience in user-product interaction.

- Based on the interviews that were carried out with each user, different opinions and comments were collected about the device appearance, usability and value. In addition, the most important problems were identified.

Regarding the device appearance, it was obvious that the appearance of a device was more acceptable among males than females. The results of the interviews with the participants showed that the device appearance has many problems, such as; the belt color is unpleasant, the form of the device is not

attractive, and the size of the device is big. As for the problems of the device usability, female participants had more negative feelings than male participants during their use of a device. The results of the behavioral evaluation level revealed that there are several problems related to the device usability, such as; a) the belt material is not soft, b) the color of the belt is dark, so that it gets dirty very easy and is difficult to clean, c) the start button is not recognized easily, and d) the users should do many steps in order to measure their blood pressure.

Regarding the users' opinions on the device value, four points we got from the users, include: the device is easy to use, but it does not have pleasant appearance. It has good function, but it is not somewhat attractive. It does not express the user

Figure 4. The results of Kansei sheets and RBL sheet

personality well. The user did not have any special feeling about it.

In the end of the first stage, we found that most of the users believe that *Kansei* sheets are easy to use and understand. In addition, the new methods are assistance, not a restriction, and therefore allow rich and amiable discussions.

Stage 2 of WS: Develop new idea/s with users

The consideration of people who are going to benefit from design during design processes is not a new concept in design practice - many humanitarian designers have emphasized this relationship. However, these relationships between designers and design users seem restricted to a quantitative approach based on measuring people's bodies and

The Device Appearance

The Device Usability

The Device Value

- | | | | | | |
|----------------|---------------|--------------|--------------|----------------|----------|
| (m) Shame | (l) Annoyance | (k) Surprise | (j) Anger | (i) Sadness | (h) Fear |
| (f) Attraction | (e) Satisfy | (d) Joy | (c) Surprise | (b) Hesitation | (a) Wish |
| (g) Neutral | (n) Other | | | | |

1, 2, 3, and 4 (the degrees of emotional responses are; 10%, 30%, 70%, and 100% respectively)

- Female
- Male

Figure 5. Analysis of the users' answers

analyzing the usability of designs in relationship with people’s abilities or disabilities.

Gradually, this ‘designing for’ approach has been challenged. Recently, there is a new democratic design development, which encourages designing ‘with’ people. This indicates that design practices should also consider people’s emotions rather than only their capabilities to use design.

In the workshop, we tried to consider users’ emotions and physical abilities. The results of the first stage detected that two issues should be regarded for designing appropriate and pleasant a BP device. First issue is related to the belt material and color, and the device size is the second one. We divided the participants into two groups. Each group included 5 people as follows; 2 users, 2 designers, and 1 WS member. Different ideas were proposed with users in order to develop the design of a BP, including its size and belt (Figure 6).

including its size and belt (Figure 6).

Stage 3 of WS: Present the best idea/s

In the third stage of the workshop, the best idea/ s were presented and discussed with all the workshop participants. Basically the best proposal characterizes by several features as follows; small size, easy to use, and attractive. As for the first and second features, the size of the new design is small enough to be kept it in the users’ bag, so that it can be used easily in everywhere. In addition, the new design can be operated easily because it is provided with clear and enough instructions. Regarding the third feature, the new design of the BP device considers the belt quality and color. It was selected carefully in order to match the users’ tastes and preferences.

Overall, this study tried to emphasis on the importance of understanding users’ emotions and

Figure 6. Developing and Presenting Different Ideas

experiences throughout the design process. The intention is to design pleasant and appropriate design that fits their emotional, physical needs and life styles (including their life, homes, and the context within which they operate).

CONCLUSIONS

People interact with products with emotion. The products can elicit strong emotional responses and these emotions influence both the decisions to purchase it and the pleasure of owning and using it after purchase. Therefore measuring emotions are essential to create pleasant design.

The present study aimed to introduce two emotional evaluation methods. The novel methods were proposed to examine and interpret users' emotions, while their interaction with the products.

The results of this study revealed the following;

- 1) both "Kansei Sheets and RBL sheet" are effective ways to understand users' experiences (UX) and needs. The users find expressing their emotions using Kansei sheets pleasant tasks, in contrast to the difficulty of expressing their emotional reactions in words. Furthermore, we found that using the two methods are convenient to create an informal atmosphere in which the users feel free to discuss experiential aspects of a product.
- 2) For capturing "UX" successfully, "triangulation" of methods is important to be used. In other words, designers should pay a close attention to collect information in different ways and comparing the results. The results of this study reveal that however "direct observation" is an appropriate method to identify the user's problems, and also to break the ice between user and design, it is not often an effective way to understand user emotions and experiences.

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